

THE IMPORTANCE OF INTERACTIVE METHOD IN TEACHING ENGLISH LANGUAGE IN UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract: This article discusses the importance of interactive methods in teaching foreign languages in New Uzbekistan, the significance of using this type of way and normative legal documents, and the advantages of using internet platforms and language norms during the establishment of the third Renaissance.

Keywords: Renaissance, New Uzbekistan, mandatory feedback, cognitive,, information, internet, information technologies, internet sites, group experience, communicative activities, people's interests, quality education in learning foreign languages.

Introduction to the interactive methods and Its Relevance

Before analyzing the role and significance of using interactive methods in teaching the foreign languages and using information technology in learning process of Uzbekistan as part of the Third Renaissance, it is important to understand the term 'interactive.' So, what is interactive way ? What contributed to its emergence?

The aim of the article is to define the main role of interactive methods of teaching languages. the term interactive means that people work together and have an influence on each other. These methods are aimed at the interaction between students and teacher as well as among students only. the purpose of interactive learning is to create some special contioions leading to the involement of all the students into the learning process in which the participants can understand and realize everything that happens, influence each other and make their own contribution having established the friendly and mutually supportive realationship. The most popular methods are role plays, brainstorming, case study method, and discussion. they develop communicative skills, logical thinking, and different types of intellectual activity such as analyses, synthesis, comparision, and generalization. these students centre methods are highly suitable in acquiring knowledge and strategies.

There are some ideas of brainstorming activities;

Multi purpose activities

First, the teacher gives the whole class any objects. Next, give the students a couple of minutes to think of all the different uses for that item. In about five minutes, the teacher asks students to share what they have come up with. For example, you can use forks to eat, comb your hair, clean plates. Not so bad for a simple fork. Using the multi-purpose items encourages creativity and it is fun to hear.

President Shavkat Mirziyoyev, in an interview with the newspaper 'New Uzbekistan,' expressed: 'Currently, another significant process of revival is taking place in our country. Therefore, the terms "New Uzbekistan" and "Third Renaissance" resonate in harmony in our lives, inspiring our people towards great aspirations.'

Strategic Goals and the Role of methods

After representing the given methods we can conclude that interactive teaching methods contribute to optimizing the learning process in studying English. They intend to put mechanism for motivation in place and increase the efficiency of teaching language communication. The advantages of using interactive methods in the process of learning include the maximum approximation to the real conditions of activity, the broad autonomy of learners, decision making in conditions of creative completion and the development of organizational skills of students, overcoming the barrier between the study of language and its practical application.

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